

Determination of Stability Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Complexes of 3-Acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-pyrone (Dehydracetic Acid)

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Manuscript received 3 July 1980, revised 28 July 1982, accepted 28 January 1983

Dissociation constants of dehydracetic acid (DHA), a physiologically active compound, and the stability constants of its complexes with certain bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically at various temperatures in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water medium and at four different ionic strengths. The weighted least squares method has been used to determine the stability constants. The values of thermodynamic stability constants and other thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been calculated. Ligand field stabilization energy, δH , has also been calculated using George and McClure method.

3-ACETYL-4-HYDROXY-6-METHYL-2-PYRONE (dehydracetic acid, DHA), with an α -pyrone structure, is a physiologically active substance and is used as fungicide, fungistatic, toxic to microorganisms. Very little work has been reported on its complexing behaviour with metal ions. The present communication deals with the determination of stability constants and other thermodynamic functions of DHA complexes with certain bivalent metal ions. The investigations have been carried out under different experimental conditions of temperature and ionic concentration. The thermodynamic parameters such as change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated. Ligand field stabilization energy (δH), has also been calculated.

Experimental

A Beckman pH meter, Model SS-2, with a glass electrode (0-14 pH range) and a calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. The pH meter was standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate and phosphate buffers.

A Thermostat, MLW (type NBE) GDR, was used for maintaining the temperature constant. IBM 360 computer was used for the calculation of stability constants and other required data.

Dehydracetic acid of reagent grade was obtained from Koch Light (England) and recrystallized from ethanol. Its solution was prepared in dioxane (E. Merck or BDH), freshly distilled over sodium. All the metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal sulphates or nitrates (A.R. quality) in double distilled water and were further standardised by conventional methods. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) solution (2 M) was used to maintain the desired ionic strength (μ). A standardised solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck) in 50% dioxane-

water medium was used as titrant. The dioxane was purified before use, by refluxing for 24 hr over sodium metal and was always freshly distilled. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Nitrogen gas, presaturated with 50% dioxane, was passed through the titrating solutions during all titrations.

Titration procedure: The method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine \bar{n} and pL values. The following solutions were titrated against 0.05 M TMAH solution in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water medium.

Set I: Ionic strength (μ) = 0.2 M, temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$

(i) 1.0 ml HClO_4 (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2 M) + 0.5 ml KNO_3 or K_2SO_4 (0.02 M) + 6.5 ml H_2O + 10 ml dioxane,

(ii) 1.0 ml HClO_4 (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2 M) + 0.5 ml KNO_3 or K_2SO_4 (0.02 M) + 3.5 ml H_2O + 6.0 ml DHA (M/120) in 50% dioxane- H_2O + 7.0 ml dioxane.

(iii) 1 ml HClO_4 (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2.0 M) + 0.5 ml metal nitrate or sulphate (0.02 M) + 3.5 ml H_2O + 6.0 ml DHA (M/120) in 50% dioxane- H_2O + 7.0 ml dioxane.

In sets II, III and IV, requisite amounts of NaClO_4 solution were added to maintain ionic strengths at 0.1, 0.05 and 0.01 M, respectively. To study the effect of temperature, the set II was repeated at 45 and $60 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Corrections for change in volume, on mixing dioxane and aqueous solutions (total volume = 19.67 ml due to contraction on mixing) as well as change in volume which took place during the course of titrations, were made in all the cases.

Calculations: \bar{n} and pL values were calculated as mentioned earlier². These values have been utilized for the computation of β_n and S_{mla} values

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES OF DHA AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS (μ) AND DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Ionic strength and Temp. (°C)		H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
$\mu=0.2$	log K ₁	6.0	5.64	4.64	4.32	3.97	3.96	3.25	3.30	2.50
(30)	log K ₂	—	5.27	4.54	4.17	3.76	3.60	3.09	3.11	2.23
$\mu=0.1$	log K ₁	6.33	5.90	4.97	4.51	4.18	4.10	3.33	3.44	2.70
(30)	log K ₂	—	5.40	4.69	4.23	4.08	4.00	3.26	3.28	2.43
$\mu=0.05$	log K ₁	6.52	5.99	5.25	4.65	4.31	4.25	3.45	3.51	2.86
(30)	log K ₂	—	5.57	5.10	4.60	4.22	4.04	3.40	3.36	2.84
$\mu=0.01$	log K ₁	6.80	6.22	5.47	4.86	4.50	4.40	3.56	3.67	3.08
(30)	log K ₂	—	5.65	5.27	4.74	4.24	4.21	3.45	3.43	3.03
$\mu=0.1$	log K ₁	5.90	5.49	4.75	4.40	4.06	3.83	3.15	3.25	2.43
(45)	log K ₂	—	5.25	4.40	3.87	3.81	3.58	3.00	3.16	2.25
$\mu=0.1$	log K ₁	5.75	5.37	4.63	4.24	3.88	3.62	3.05	3.17	2.33
(60)	log K ₂	—	4.96	4.06	3.79	3.48	3.43	2.82	3.02	2.13

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND LIGAND FIELD STABILIZATION ENERGY (δH) VALUES FOR THE DHA-METAL (BIVALENT) COMPLEXES

Parameters	Mn ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁ ⁰	3.60	4.63	5.02	5.73	6.30	4.55	—	—
— ΔG°	4.99	6.42	6.96	7.94	8.73	6.31	—	—
(k cal mole ⁻¹)								
δH	—	17.00	25.00	36.00	28.00	—	—	—
— ΔG°	9.1	11.4	12.1	13.4	15.7	11.2	9.3	7.1
(k cal mole ⁻¹)								
— ΔH	0.48	0.64	0.52	0.68	0.72	0.64	0.56	0.40
(k cal mole ⁻¹)								
ΔS	29	36	38	42	49	35	29	22
(cal.deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)								

ΔG° and δH calculated using log K₁⁰ values at 30 ± 0.5° and ΔG° values calculated using log β_2 values at 30 ± 0.5°.

using weighted least squares method of Sullivan *et al.*³.

The values of thermodynamic stability constants, log K₁⁰, were obtained by extrapolating the curve of log K₁ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ up to $\sqrt{\mu}=0.0$. Utilizing these values of log K₁⁰, the ligand field stabilization energy δH has been calculated using George and McClure method⁴ (Table 2). Thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , have also been calculated (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The values of log K_n (Table 1) reflect the following trends :

- (i) The values of log K₁ fall gradually from copper to magnesium, and the following order has been obtained : Cu > Ni > Co > Fe > Zn > Cd > Mn > Mg. This order is in good agreement with that reported by Irving and Williams⁵, and Mellor and Maley⁶.
- (ii) There is regular increase in the values of stability constants with dilution of the

inert electrolyte and with decreasing temperature (Table 1), which is a general trend.

- (iii) The ligand field stabilization energy (δH) values (Table 2) are found in the order Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) > Cu(II).
- (iv) Negative values of ΔG and ΔH and increase in entropy (ΔS) (Table 2) indicate spontaneous complexation of the ligand with the bivalent metal ions.

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